

THE CONTENT OF THE FORMATION OF LINGUISTIC COMPETENCIES IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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***Abstract.** Linguistic development of elementary school students from the first stages of the general education process is one of the most important issues. For this reason, this article is devoted to clarifying the essence of the formation of linguistic competences in elementary school students.*

***Keywords:** Competence, linguistic competence, primary school classes, primary school students, general education process.*

In today's rapidly changing and advanced information and communication technologies, educating the young generation as a highly spiritual and intellectually developed person is one of the priority directions of state policy.

Reforms in this direction are implemented within the framework of the "On Education" and similar Laws and large-scale national programs, and are recognized by the developed countries of the world and international organizations.

First of all, the effectiveness of the educational process depends on the high-quality fulfillment of the requirements of the State educational standards and educational programs developed on the basis of today's demand, the needs of society, the development trends of science and technology.

The Uzbek people have paid great attention to science since ancient times and tried to develop it. Ibn Sina, Beruni, Al-Khorazmi, Amir Temur, Ulugbek and many other scholars introduced science to the world. Our people, who have great respect for knowledge, wish their children to be literate, no matter what difficulties and obstacles there are. They sent their children to school from a young age. School teachers taught children based on their methods and experience. So, in Uzbekistan, there were specific methods of teaching and they were developing. This process was not smooth. Some errors and omissions were made.

In the process of learning the native language, the material that serves as the basis for teaching the native language at school is especially valuable in solving the issue of forming the foundations of a scientific worldview in students. The real side of the material, its ideological orientation and artistic expressiveness affect the students' thinking and emotions, expand their knowledge about the environment, cultivate interest in the language and the people who created it, and the general development of the students. increases their level and affects the formation of their personal qualities and outlook. In the following years, the requirements for the content of the material of mother tongue textbooks and manuals published for teachers have increased in number and quality.

The main criterion of the material is the knowledge-enriching value of the text and individual sentences, lexical and stylistic accuracy, thematic diversity, connection with different aspects of life, ideological and thematic orientation of the texts, suitability for young students. The implementation of such requirements, in addition to the development of the main types of speech activity in elementary school students, provides for the solution of the following important

issues. First of all, the content of the knowledge given in the mother tongue in the elementary grades is about the sound structure of the Uzbek language and the ways of expressing sounds in written speech, about the change of words and the connection of words in a sentence, the morphemic composition of words and words formation, the lexical-semantic group of words, the correct writing rules of the Uzbek language and the use of punctuation marks. The given knowledge serves to develop students' speech. The content and methods of teaching the mother tongue should help students to acquire thorough knowledge, skills, and abilities in the amount required by the program.

The main task of teaching the science of the mother tongue is the development of speech competence aimed at thinking of the student's personality, understanding the opinion of others, being able to express one's opinion in oral and written form, students' knowledge of grammar (phonetics, lexicology, word structure, word formation, morphology, syntax, writing and spelling, punctuation, speech styles, stylistic concepts) formation and development and using the wide possibilities of the native language to speak what they have read, seen and heard consists of forming linguistic competences aimed at developing the skills of correct and fluent expression. The curriculum of the subject of the mother tongue was created based on the requirements of the State Education Standard aimed at the formation of competencies in students. The training program envisages the formation of speech and linguistic competences and elements of basic competences in students. In primary education, it is to ensure students' literacy, to form compliance with the standards of literary speech in oral and written speech.

Today, the terms competence, linguistic competence approach have entered education and are rapidly becoming popular. In linguistics, this term was used for the first time in the middle of the 20th century and was interpreted as a set of knowledge, skills and abilities oriented to the activity in the process of using the language. In this case, the concepts of competence and competence approach are noted as factors that indicate effectiveness in education.

In the developed countries of the world in the 21st century, as one of the main directions of modernization of the content of education, the main attention is paid to the issue of introducing the competence approach in education.

Education based on the competence approach is education aimed at forming the competencies of students to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications in their personal, professional and social activities.

Based on the continuity of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan and its focus on educating a well-rounded person, basic competencies in order to ensure the consistency of the content of general education subjects taught in general secondary, secondary special, vocational education and based on the content of each academic subject, general competences related to the subject were determined. In particular, the task of forming competencies related to a specific subject was included in this content.

The essential change of the learning and teaching process with the demands of the times is the revision of the previously existing three-category system of "knowledge", "skills" and "qualifications" and a new approach aimed at evaluating the results in education. led to its introduction. Competency levels (or competency levels) obtained in each subject at a certain educational stage are the ability to apply acquired knowledge, practical skills and personal qualities for temporary work in a certain field, and this is not only the acquired theoretical knowledge, but

also It is a complex of knowledge and skills, but also the level of independent and creative application of acquired theoretical and practical knowledge to practice.

According to scientific pedagogical and psychological sources, competence and competence are very complex, multi-part, common concepts for a number of disciplines. Therefore, its interpretations are different both in terms of volume, content, and content of meaning and logic. the essence of the term is described on the basis of such concepts as "efficiency", "adaptability", "achievement", "readability", "quality", «quantity".

Based on this, it is important to prepare the ground for today's pedagogues to be able to independently apply the knowledge taught to students in daily activities, to analyze practical activities in the formation of a number of competencies in students, in particular, linguistic competencies.

In the modern education system, education of a free person through the formation of competence knowledge, formation of the ability to think independently in the representatives of the future generation, acquisition and application of knowledge, quick and careful thinking of the decisions to be made and accurate planning of actions, effective cooperation in different groups, open to new contacts more attention is paid to being. This requires a wide introduction of alternative forms and methods of acquiring competence skills along with learning activities into the educational process. In this case, the use of new pedagogical tools such as interactive methods, multimedia, etc. in the course of the lesson will also give effective results.

This research work plays a big role in developing students' talents and educating them as well-rounded people. For example, in the process of preparing for various events and mornings, it requires having deeper knowledge than what is acquired in the basic course of science. Focusing on students' mental creative activities has a stimulating effect on increasing the efficiency of the educational process and developing individual talent. Talented students gain experience of intellectual leadership by participating in science exams and Olympiads and achieving positive results. Organization of extracurricular activities is also very important in the development of students' talents.

In particular, in the processes of each lesson organized in the subject of the mother tongue, the elements of competence in the subject are developed, using methods such as distance learning, virtual laboratory, video conferences, webinars, appropriate to the age characteristics of primary school students. Traditionally, every year in educational institutions, holding the week of information and communication technologies, conducting the initial stages of the "Knowledgers" and "Zakovat" clubs among primary school students is effective in forming children's interest in knowledge, increasing their knowledge of nature and existence, and developing their creative activities. is considered Such events can be organized in several directions:

- career guidance;
- educational and research;
- information and entertainment; quizzes;
- intellectually playful and others.

Through these methods, elements of competence related to science, such as speech, quick thinking, listening and speaking, and communication are formed. In order to identify the talents of students in all fields of science and art, the wide use of the following forms in extracurricular activities will be the foundation for deep instilling of competence knowledge related to science:

exhibitions of children's art, creative review contests, frequent holding of science-related competitions, etc.

Summarizing the above-mentioned points, it is possible to achieve very important and urgent results by focusing on the formation of competences related to science with an innovative approach to classes and extracurricular activities conducted in such a way. For example, as a result of this, it is possible to help students increase their interest in science and establish emotional ties between them. Also, by teaching them to work in a team, to develop students' speech, to enrich their vocabulary with new words, to listen to the opinions of their peers, the fulfillment of educational tasks is ensured.

REFERENCES

1. Dilshoda Jalilova Ural qizi. BO‘LAJAK BOSHLANG‘ICH SINFI O‘QITUVCHILARIDA AXBOROT KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MASALASINING AHAMIYATI. RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR DAVRIDA TILLARNI INTENSIV O‘QITISHNING PSIXOLOGIK- PEDAGOGIK JIHLTLARI RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI. 2023-yil 2-iyun (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7993607>)
2. Jalilova D.U. Psychological And Technological Features of Increasing the Efficiency of Educational Activity of Talented Students in Presidential Schools. Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices ISSN NO: 2770-2367 (<https://zienjournals.com>).
3. Mahfuza Tursunqulova To‘lqin qizi. ZAMONAVIY TA‘LIM SHAROITIDA O‘QUVCHILARIDA LINGVISTIK KOMPETENSIYALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH MASALASI VA YONDASHUVNING AHAMIYATI UYG‘UNLIGI. “RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR DAVRIDA TILLARNI INTENSIV O‘QITISHNING PSIXOLOGIK- PEDAGOGIK JIHLTLARI” MAVZUSIDAGI RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI. 01.06.2023 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7993657>.
4. Страйнберг Дж. 110 игр на уроках английского языка: Пер. с англ. – М.: Издательство Астрель, 2004./124 с.
5. Tursunqulova Maxfuza To‘lqin qizi. BOSHLANG‘ICH SINFLARDA FOYDALANILADIGAN DIDAKTIK O‘YINLAR HAQIDA AYRIM MULOHAZALAR. YANGILANAYOTGAN O‘ZBEKISTON TARAQQIYOTIDA IQTISODIY FANLARNI O‘QITISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8044429/>
<http://scientists.uz/uploads/conferences/007/1.94.pdf>
6. Tursunqulova Maxfuza To‘lqin qizi. BOSHLANG‘ICH SINFLARDA FOYDALANILADIGAN DIDAKTIK O‘YINLAR HAQIDA AYRIM MULOHAZALAR. YANGILANAYOTGAN O‘ZBEKISTON TARAQQIYOTIDA IQTISODIY FANLARNI O‘QITISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI. 15.06.2023 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8044429>
7. G‘afforova T. , Nurullayeva Sh. Boshlang'ich sinflar ona tili darslarida didaktik o‘yinlar va mustaqil ishlar. –Qarshi: Nasaf, 2003. –54 b.
8. https://t.me/jalilova_dilshoda_2292
9. https://t.me/ilmiy_yordam_beraman